

Open Research Infrastructure - CRMM

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1 Introduction

Replication is an important pillar in academic research (Open Science Collaboration, 2015). Open Science (UNESCO & Canadian National Commission for UNESCO, 2022) has a role in replication as in reuse of knowledge (Hevner et al., 2024; Maedche et al., 2024).

We prefer open source, open access and open science to maximize the opportunity for replication. For example: When access to software or a literature database demands a (high) license costs, this will limit the replication of our research.

Part of open science is the open research infrastructure. We define research infrastructure as the tooling we used to support our processes in our knowledge creation during our research journey.

We like to share our research infrastructure which we developed in the past years during our research for a Cyber Resilience Maturity Model (CRMM), in support of replication and in support of sharing knowledge. This report is an addition to the existing corpus (Brinkman et al., 2023; Teplitzky et al., 2021) on how to start using open science in your research.

1.1 Replication

For researchers to replicate a study, Steeves, 2017 identifies necessary factors. At the baseline is **reviewable research**, which offers sufficient detail for assessment. This progresses to **replicable research**, where tools are available to duplicate

results using the original data, and **confirmable research**, where conclusions can be reached independently without the author’s resources. To ensure integrity, auditable research requires that all processes, data, and artifacts are archived for future defense. Finally, open and reproducible research, defined as **auditable research** that is fully accessible to the public.

1.2 Knowledge

The goal of academic research is to create knowledge through the integration of abduction, deduction, and induction. Our research into CRMM represents a multi-year evolution from Master’s level to doctoral research. Our research strategy relies on collecting varied data sources to iteratively build and verify individual mental models. We use various (scholarly) artifacts to align these views into shared mental models (fig 1). Our research infrastructure supports this cycle of knowledge creation. The description of the social support system is out of scope of this report.

Figure 1: Knowledge Deliverables to be supported

2 Selection

In our effort to find, assess and select tooling and processes we used various sources which provide an overview of existing open science tools and taxonomy (e.g. Guide, 2026; Vandegrift and Vandegrift, 2019; Vergoulis and Chatzopoulos, 2023). In this section our selection.

2.1 Open Science Framework

Knowledge creation involves an iterative process of divergence and convergence. Inspired by the Open Science Framework by the Center for Open Science, 2026 and the UNESCO and Canadian National Commission for UNESCO, 2022 recommendation on open science, we adopted a four-phased framework (fig 2). The first phase, **Search and Discover**, involves iterating on idea development and exploring existing literature. This is followed by **Design Study**, which entails setting up and structuring the project and pre-registering the analysis plan. The third phase, **Collect and Analyze Data**, covers the acquisition, storage, and processing of materials, supported by open data management protocols. The final phase, **Publish Reports**, focuses on publishing the full research output, including reports, data, code, and materials, via open access channels to maximize discoverability.

Figure 2: Conceptual model of Open Science Framework of the research process

2.2 Search and Discover

To developing ideas and and explore existing research, you need to be able to search, ideate, write, publish and collaborate.

For exploratory literature research using keywords, article suggestion and forward- and backward snowballing (Wohlin, 2014) we used various open databases, which did not require a fee to access the search functionality (see table 1). These databases returned open access as well proprietary documents in their search results.

To manage the research results (see table 2), we used Zotero, 2024 as reference manager. For collaboration with Zotero one of our team members acquired a paid subscription. To search through the acquired (open access) documents we used Recoll, 2023 as search engine. To enrich the meta-data, of all references managed in Zotero, we used BibTeX-autocomplete, 2023.

For Note-taking we wrote (clear-text) markdown files using the editor Kate and the editor Sublime on a laptop. With Git we tracked the changes and pushed the files from the local machine into the wiki repository of a GitLab project. For spelling and grammar advice we installed on the laptop LanguageTool, and used Open AI, Google Gemini and Mistral AI for advice on different phrasing and paragraph shorting. We invited people to collaborate, with our ideation, via the Git Project hosted at GitLab or via sharing presentations (see table 3).

Through the years we used Chrome OS, Fedora, Arch and Ubuntu as operating system on the laptops for Note-taking (see table 6).

To create images, during the ideation when Note-taking, we used Google Slides, and GIMP as image editor (see table 4).

For interviews, research practice meetings, research courses, etc we used mainly Microsoft teams (provided by the university), Google Meet, Zoom, or Signal. As backup we had Jitsi, for when we needed to collaborate with a person that would or could not use the proprietary communication tools (see table 5).

2.3 Design Study

For the design and management of our project we used Google Slides, Google Sheets (see table 7), and by writing research proposals (see table 8).

For writing the research proposal we used Overleaf in combination with local writing in \LaTeX . To be able to collaborate in Overleaf, a team member acquired a paid license. For text editing we used the same tooling as for writing wiki pages in markdown and creating images (see table 3). The local files were versioned using Git and synchronized with the projects in Overleaf and a backup project in GitLab. We used Microsoft Word for internal communication at the university as part of the provided subscription, and for the final submission of draft papers to conferences (see table 8).

For compiling \LaTeX code into PDF files, we used overleaf when online, and to compile on the local device, we used a stack of existing tooling, leading to a very pleasant writing experience, which refreshed the PDF with every textual change (see table 9). The stack is defined by an existing project called latex-pipeline, where a docker container managed by the Tex Live community is used to generate PDF continuously from the TeX files. For local PDF viewing we used Evince (see table 9).

Note: faculty members are using Laptops using Microsoft Windows, for providing feedback on research proposals and draft papers.

2.4 Collect and Analyze Data

For the collection of data we used the earlier mentioned Markdown files in the GitLab wiki (see table 3). We also created various research notes, to structure the results out of the ideation phase (see tables 7, 8, 9).

2.5 Publish Reports

For publishing our work we use various ways (see table 11). We used the public access to our GitLab Wiki to provide insight in our research Progress. To publish our open data sets, we used a website hosted at GitLab page, generated from Markdown files into static HTML pages by HUGO.

We created authors accounts on ORCID, Google Scholar and Research Gate to increase the exposure and findability of our published work. With the ORCID account we create an account on Zenodo, 2013, which is hosted by CERN and funded by the EU OpenAir. The EU did this in support of Open Science by delivering a public and open repository for dataset, white-papers, research-notes and other research information products.

3 License

Adhering to Open Science (Hevner et al., 2024; Maedche et al., 2024) and FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016), this report is published as plain text \LaTeX on Zenodo, 2013 under the Creative Commons BY-SA 4.0 license. We thank Aaron Tay, 2021, Cecile Janssens, 2021 and Ujjal Marjit, 2022 for their inspiring blogs on literature research and Schmidt, 2020 for highlighting the relevance of providing open access.

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Table 1: Search & Discover - Exploratory Literature Research

Citation Chaser	Free to use; Open Source (GitHub) Open Data from lens.org
Citation Gecko	Free to use; Open Source (GitHub) Open Data from Crossref and Open Citations
Connected Papers	Free to use (Freemium); Open Source (GitHub) Open Data from Semantic Scholar
LitMaps	Free to use (Freemium); Closed Source Open Data from Crossref , Semantic Scholar and OpenAlex
OpenKnowledge Map	Free to use; Open Source (GitHub) Open data from PubMed and BASE
Research Gate	Free to use (Freemium); Closed Source Open Data uploaded by users.
Research Rabbit	Free to use (Freemium); Closed Source Open data from Crossref , Semantic Scholar , and OpenAlex
OA.mg	Free to use (Freemium); Closed Source Open Data from OpenAlex , CrossRef , arXiv , Scite , CORE , Simeh , FatCat , DiVA , ORCID , Dynamica , DOAJ , ROR , WikiData , AMiner , OpenAccessButton , PaperPanda , Unpaywall , Pubmed , Zenodo , Litmaps , The ISSN International Centre , Citationsy , and Semantic Scholar
Google Scholar	Free to use; Closed Source Aims to index all data
OpenAI ChatGTP	Free to use; Closed Source Unknown data sources and reliability.
Google Gemini	Free to use; Closed Source Unknown data sources and reliability.

Table 2: Search & Discover - Reference Management

Zotero	Local Reference Manager to manage collected documents. Free to use (freemium); Open Source (GitHub) Runs on Linux, macOS, Microsoft Windows, Google Android OS and Apple iOS, iPadOS.
Recoll	Local Search Engine to search through collected documents. Free to use; Open Source (Framagit GitLab) Runs on Linux, macOS and Microsoft Windows.
BibTeX AutoComplete	Enriches Meta Data of collected documents. Free to use; Open Source (GitHub) Open Data from OpenAlex , CrossRef , ArXiv , Semantic Scholar , UnPayWall , DBLP , ResearchR , InspireHEP . Runs on every machine that runs Python

Table 3: Search & Discover - Open Note-taking

Kate	<p>Text Editor Free to use; Open Source (KDE Gitlab) Runs on Linux, macOS, Microsoft Windows. Actively maintained since 2001</p>
Sublime Text	<p>Text Editor Free to use (Shareware); Closed Source Runs on Linux, macOS, Microsoft Windows. Actively maintained since 2008</p>
Markdown	<p>Text Format Free to use; Open Source (GitHub) Markdown is a lightweight clear text markup language. Actively maintained since 2004 Widely used standard since 2019</p>
LanguageTool	<p>Text Spelling Free to use; Open Source (GitHub); Actively maintained since 2005</p>
OpenAI ChatGTP	<p>Text Rephrasing Free to use; Closed Source SaaS offering used.</p>
Google Gemini	<p>Text Rephrasing Free to use; Closed Source SaaS offering used.</p>
Mistral AI	<p>Text Reduction Free to use; Closed Source SaaS offering used.</p>
Git	<p>Text Versioning Free to use; Open Source (Kernel.org) Actively maintained since 2005 Widely used standard since 2015</p>
GitLab Wiki	<p>SaaS offering used for Note Publishing Free to use (Freemium) Open Source (GitLab) Actively maintained since 2011</p>

Table 4: Search & Discover - Images

Google Slides	<p>SaaS offering used for Image Creation Free to use (Freemium); Closed Source;</p>
GIMP	<p>used for Image Manipulation, e.g. setting transparency Free to use; Open Source (GNOME GitLab);</p>

Table 5: Search & Discover - Video Conferencing

Microsoft Teams	SaaS offering used for Video Conferencing Free to use (Freemium); Closed Source Part of university application portfolio (payed version);
Google Meet	SaaS offering used for Video Conferencing Free to use (Freemium); Closed Source
Zoom	SaaS offering used for Video Conferencing Free to use (Freemium); Closed Source
Jitsi	SaaS offering used for Video Conferencing Free to use; Open Source (GitHub) Runs on Linux, macOS, Microsoft Windows, Google Android OS, and Apple iOS, iPadOS, and watchOS. Actively maintained since 2003
Signal	used for Video Conferencing Free to use; Open Source (GitHub) Runs on Linux, macOS, Microsoft Windows, Google Android OS and Apple iOS. Actively maintained since 2014

Table 6: Search & Discover - Computer Operating System

Chrome OS	Usage is limited to owning a Chromebook; Closed Source
Fedora Linux	Free to use; Open Source (Pagure @RedHat) Actively maintained since 2003
Ubuntu Linux	Free to use; Open Source (Launchpad @ Canonical) Actively maintained since 2004
Arch Linux	Free to use; Open Source (GitLab , and GitHub) Actively maintained since 2002

Table 7: Design Study - Project Management

Google Slides	SaaS offering used for creating, visualizing and sharing Project Planning . Free to use (Freemium); Closed Source;
Google Sheets	SaaS offering used for creating, visualizing and sharing Project Planning . Free to use (Freemium); Closed Source;

Table 8: Design Study - Project Proposal

Writing Tools	See Open Note-taking Tools at Search and Discover
GitLab Repository	SaaS offering used for Versioning Free to use (Freemium) Open Source (GitLab) Actively maintained since 2011
LaTeX	used as Text Format Free to use; Open Source (GitHub) Widely used standard since 1980 LaTeX provides a high-level, descriptive markup language for typesetting documents, based on TeX. TeX handles the document layout, while LaTeX handles the content side for document processing.
BibTeX	used as Text Format of the Reference Free to use; Open Source (CTAN , Tuc). Widely used standard since 1988 BibTeX is both a bibliographic flat-file database file format and a software program for processing these files to produce lists of references (citations).
Overleaf	SaaS offering used as Text Editor Free to use (freemium); Open Source (GitHub) Supports real-time collaboration, adding comments and versioning.
Microsoft Word	SaaS offering used as Text Editor Free to use (Freemium); Closed Source Part of university application portfolio (payed version);

Table 9: Design Study - Local LaTeX processing

LaTeX-Pipeline	<p>used to automate compilation of TeX project files into Project Proposal in PDF</p> <p>Free to use; Open Source (GitLab)</p> <p>Runs on Linux, macOS, Microsoft Windows</p> <p>Integration of LaTeX Tooling;</p> <p>Supports continuous rebuild of PDF on file change on local machine or via Git-hooks after push to the hosted repository</p>
TeX Live	<p>used for compilation of TeX project files into Project Proposal in PDF.</p> <p>Free to use; Open Source (Files, Docker Container image)</p> <p>Environment with all needed LaTeX libraries and tooling.</p>
Docker	<p>used for environment management of compilation of TeX project files into Project Proposal in PDF.</p> <p>Free to use (Freemium); Open Source (GitHub)</p> <p>Runs on Linux, macOS, Microsoft Windows.</p> <p>Provides the capability to run on your machine isolated environment in containers.</p>
latexmk	<p>used to automate compilation of TeX project files into Project Proposal in PDF.</p> <p>Free to use; Open Source (CTAN)</p> <p>A script that runs various tooling to compile LaTeX files into a readable PDF including bibliography. This includes monitoring files for being changed, to trigger recompile of the LaTeX files.</p>
Make	<p>used to automate compilation of TeX project files into Project Proposal in PDF.</p> <p>Free to use; Open Source (GNU)</p> <p>Tool to call complicated commands in a simple way, commonly used for build automation.</p>
Evince	<p>used to automate preview of the Project Proposal in PDF.</p> <p>Free to use; Open Source (GNOME GitLab);</p> <p>Supports continuous refresh view of PDF, PostScript, DjVu, TIFF, XPS or DVI files.</p>

Table 10: Collect & Analyze Data

Writing Tools	See Open Note-taking Tools at Search and Discover for tools used to Collect and Analyze Data
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Table 11: Publish Report

ORCID	Used to uniquely identify as (academic) Author Free to use; Open Source (GitHub) Will contribute to the reach of published work
Google Scholar	Used to uniquely identify as (academic) Author Free to use; Closed Source Will contribute to the reach of published work
Research Gate	Used to uniquely identify as (academic) Author Free to use (Freemium); Closed Source Will contribute to the reach of published work
GitLab Pages	SaaS offering used for Publishing of Research Results Free to use (Freemium) Open Source (GitLab) Actively maintained since 2011
GitLab Pipeline	SaaS offering used for automated generate static website and Publish via Gitlab Pages Free to use (Freemium) Open Source (GitLab) Actively maintained since 2011
HUGO	Used to convert Markdown files into Static HTML files for Publishing Work as website on Gitlab Pages . Free to use; Open Source (GitHub)
Zenodo	Used to Publish Work (data sets, reports, pre-prints, etc) and provides a DOI. Free to use; Open Source (GitHub) Zenodo is a general-purpose open repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN in support of Open Science. Actively maintained since 2013